

Quality Assessment of Groundwater System using Geochemical Parameters in Wamakko Town, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Geochemical parameters studies on groundwater quality of Wamakko Town were undertaken. The objectives of the study were to determine the concentration of the anion and cation in the water samples, to determine the effect of interactions between the groundwater and the aquifer or surface contamination, and to compare the concentration level with WHO standard. The geochemical study was carried out on 10 water samples from different locations. The geochemical analyses involved the application of Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS), Flame spectrophotometer and titration in chemical units. The cations concentration values for Ca^{2+} ranges from 12.50 to 18.60 with an average (16.18 mg/l), Mg^{2+} concentration varies from 3.20 to 5.50 mg/l with an average of 3.636 mg/l, Fe^{2+} content vary from 0.020 to 0.042 mg/l with an average values of 0.0295 mg/l, Cu^{2+} contents vary from 0.20 to 0.53 mg/l with an average of 0.375 mg/l, Zn^{2+} contraction values vary from 0.020 to 0.060 with an average (0.0421 mg/l) and Mn^{2+} from 0.035 to 0.048 mg/l with an average values of 0.0415 mg/l; all within the safety limits of WHO standard. The anions also show similar trend with those of cations, but characterized by anomalous values in PO_4 , and NH_4 , with average concentration values of 0.88 and 3.7 mg/l compared with WHO standard limit of 0.50 and 0.30 mg/l respectively. The high concentration values in the anions were as a result of anthropogenic means like decomposition of fertilizer for planting and possibly the marine environment of deposition in the case of PO_4 ion. The anomaly recorded in the PO_4 and NH_4 , made the groundwater unsuitable for consumption to the residents of Wamakko Town. It is suggested that the water should be treated to reduce the anomalous concentration levels of PO_4 and NH_4 to tolerable level in order to avoid health hazard in the community.

Keywords: Aquifer, Anthropogenic means, Geochemical parameters, Marine environment, Surface contamination

1.0 Introduction

Kalambaina Formation was an integral part of what was used to be known as Sokoto Group. However, the use of the terminology of Sokoto Group was abolished in the work of [1] and the research output of [2]). This was due to age discrepancies in the three formations which was thought to belong to the Paleocene Group [3]. The Kalambaina Formation was recently dated based on the recovery of pollen and spores to belong to Early Maastrichtian to Paleocene age [1], and on the basis of foraminiferal marker forms, dated Maastrichtian to Paleocene age [2].

The Kalambaina Formation is composed mainly of limestone and shale, with sandstone facies at the top of it which separates it from the Gamba Formation at BUA Cement Quarry, Wamakko Village [4]. Therefore, the main aquifer in the Kalambaina Formation are the carbonate rocks which consist of limestone beds. Studies on the hydrochemistry of Kalambaina Formation are not well documented in literature. However, few works available include those of [5,6].

Recent works include those of [7,8]. Other researchers who have worked on the groundwater of Sokoto Basin but not in particular on

Kalambaina Formation include [9, 6, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17].

Alagbe [7] posited that the aquifer in the Kalambaina Formation is recharged by rain water, while the K⁺ and NO₃⁻ were considered to be on a high side when compared with WHO standard limits. However, [8] concentrated more on the hydraulic conductivity of the Kalambaina Formation, whereby, the transmissivity capacity for the Kalambaina Formation was 140.00×10m²/s/m and the yield was described to be high in groundwater resources.

Wali *et al.* [15] considered the shallow groundwater in the Cretaceous and Tertiary

aquifers in northern Kebbi State. Also, on a broader view, Wali *et al.* [16] elaborated on the hydrogeology and hydrochemistry of the Sokoto Basin, while [8] dwelled on the groundwater resources appraisals of the Bodiga and environs in Sokoto Basin. However, this present study intends to evaluate the effects of the reactions of the groundwater system with the overlying beds, the limestone aquifer and the presence of antropogenic contaminants in the Kalambaina Formation. The research is to further determine the portability of the water for the inhabitants of the Wamakko Area in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The location map of the study area is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area (Wamakko Area)

2.0 Methodology

The materials used to achieve the collection water samples for this research include topographic map of the study area, Garmin GPS for locating positions in the map, 100 m measuring tape, sterilized water bottles and sample bag to store the water samples. Ten (10) water samples, one each from the locations were collected into 75cl sterile plastic bottles from borehole, well and river for geochemical analysis. The collected water samples were acidified with drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) for

preservation in the field. The collected samples were later preserved in refrigerator for about a week before taken for analysis. The procedures followed were as described in the work of Ola-Buraimo and Ologe [17]. Geochemical analysis was carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (ASS), and Buck PFP-7 Flame Photometer.

Flame photometry is an atomic emission method for the routine detection of metal salts, principally Na and K. Quantitative analysis of these species is performed by measuring the

flame emission of solutions containing the metal salts. Solutions are aspirated into the flame. The hot flame evaporates the solvent, atomizes the metal which excites a valence electron to an upper state. Light was emitted at characteristic wavelengths for each metal as the electron returns to the ground state. Optical filters were used to select the emission wavelength monitored for the analyte species. Comparison of emission intensities of unknowns to either that of standard

solutions, or to those of an internal standard, allows quantitative analysis of the analyte metal in the sample solutions.

3.0 Result and Interpretation

The sample locations and their respective location coordinates are presented in Table 1. The 10 water samples collected from Wamakko Town and their respective coordinates were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sampling locations and coordinates in Wamakko Town

S/N	Name of Location	Coordinate
Loc. 1	GidanAlu	13 ⁰ 2'0"N 5 ⁰ 7'10"E
Loc. 2	Orthopedic Quarters	13 ⁰ 2'0"N 5 ⁰ 7'10"E
Loc. 3	GidanBadamfari	13 ⁰ 2'2"N 5 ⁰ 7'6"E
Loc. 4	Gidan Dan Jeka	13 ⁰ 2'8"N 5 ⁰ 6'47"E
Loc. 5	Tudunbasu	13 ⁰ 2'18"N 5 ⁰ 6'35"E
Loc. 6	MarmaronTunga	13 ⁰ 2'23"N 5 ⁰ 6'22"E
Loc. 7	RafinHakimi	13 ⁰ 2'25"N 5 ⁰ 6'13"E
Loc. 8	ShiyarHakimi	13 ⁰ 1'53"N 5 ⁰ 6'24"E
Loc. 9	Wamakko Layout	13 ⁰ 1'53"N 5 ⁰ 6'34"E
Loc. 10	Gidan Bazamfare	13 ⁰ 2'3"N 5 ⁰ 7'14"E

Table 2: Result of geochemical analysis of water samples from Wamakko Town

Locations	Na ⁺	K	Ca	Mg	Zn	Cu	Fe	Mn	NH ₄	NO ₃	SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	F	PO ₄
LOC.1	35.2	44.1	14.8	3.20	0.033	0.24	0.030	0.042	5.2	0.043	0.044	3.22	0	0.5
LOC.2	30.2	42.5	17.5	3.50	0.052	0.53	0.033	0.046	4.4	0.042	0.130	3.38	0	1.0
LOC.3	44.2	14.2	17.3	3.20	0.056	0.44	0.024	0.034	4.3	0.053	0.143	5.43	0	0.6
LOC.4	28.1	16.0	17.5	3.56	0.050	0.36	0.030	0.035	3.6	0.035	0.053	3.35	0	0.6
LOC.5	32.4	40.0	15.8	3.50	0.040	0.34	0.042	0.044	3.8	0.037	0.050	3.25	0	0.8
LOC.6	28.4	40.0	12.5	4.30	0.020	0.42	0.024	0.042	4.4	0.045	0.033	4.46	0	1.2
LOC.7	35.4	42.2	15.7	4.60	0.040	0.30	0.020	0.038	3.2	0.040	0.027	4.52	0	0.4
LOC.8	25.4	15.2	16.4	3.45	0.060	0.52	0.032	0.046	5.2	0.035	0.024	4.33	0	0.6
LOC.9	33.2	40.2	15.7	3.55	0.030	0.20	0.030	0.048	3.5	0.020	0.150	4.42	0	0.8
LOC.10	40.2	18.5	18.6	3.50	0.040	0.40	0.030	0.040	4.5	0.043	0.043	3.46	0	0.5
Highest value	44.2	44.1	18.6	4.60	0.060	0.53	0.042	0.048	5.2	0.053	0.150	5.43	0	1.2
Lowest value	25.4	14.2	12.5	3.20	0.020	0.20	0.020	0.035	3.2	0.020	0.024	3.22	0	0.4
Average value	33.27	31.2	16.1	3.636	0.0421	0.375	0.0295	0.0415	4.21	0.0393	0.069	3.98	0	0.7
WHO mg/l	200.0	200.0	75.0	50.00	5.00	1.00	0.30	0.05	0.50	45.00	250.0	250.0	1.4	0.30
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The summary of the concentrations of dissolved elements and compounds in the groundwater collected from Wamakko Town, Sokoto State, northwestern Nigeria was presented in Table 2. Analytical results of the investigated cations and anions were compared with World Health Organization (WHO).

The geochemical analysis results of water samples obtained from Wamakko Town show that all the cations which are Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺, and Mn²⁺ concentration values are within the standard limits of WHO (2012)(Tab.

2). The sodium (Na⁺) concentrations show a minimum value of 25.4mg/l at location 8 (ShiyarHakimi) and the highest value of 44.2mg/l in location 3 (GidanBadamfari) with an average value of 33.27mg/l (Tab. 2). These values are relatively high, but far less than the maximum concentration limit specified by WHO, put at 200 mg/l.

The Potassium ion (K⁺) concentration vary between 14.2mg/l at location 3(GidanBadamfari) to44.1mg/l at location1 (GidanAlu)and an average of 31.29mg/l compared to 200mg/l of

WHO standard. Though, the K^+ concentration is relatively high in content, but safe and fall less than the maximum limit of 200 mg/l specified by [18]. The high concentration values K^+ observed in this work is in tandem with the work of [7] on Kalambaina aquifer. The relative high concentration of Na^+ and K^+ are suggested to have resulted from groundwater reaction with overburden layers of the Gamba Formation which consists of marlstone, shale, claystone and the intercalated shale between the limestone beds in the Kalambaina Formation. The sediment-fluid chemical reaction and decomposition within the overburden lithofacies were leached and permeated through the overlying beds into the limestone aquifer at the bottom.

The Calcium (Ca^{+}) varies from 12.50mg/l at location 6 (MarmaronTunga) to 18.60 mg/l at location 10 (GidanBazamfare), and an average value of 16.18 mg/l; less than the 75 mg/l specified limit by WHO. The Ca^{+} contents are still relatively high in the groundwater which suggests in situ dissolution of the limestone aquifer. Magnesium ion (Mg^{+}) concentration varies between 3.20 in locations 1 and 3 (GidanAlu and GidanBadamfari) to 4.60 mg/l at location 7 (RafinHakimi), and an average value of 3.636 mg/l, compared to 50 mg/l WHO standard limit (Tab. 2). Zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) vary in concentration from 0.020-0.060 mg/l, average value of 0.0421 mg/l compared with 5.0 mg/l specified standard limit. The Copper (Cu^{+}) ion concentration values in the water samples range from 0.20-0.53 mg/l; average value is 0.375 mg/l, compared to 1.0 mg/l recommended limit value. Thus, Cu^{+} concentrations are safe and fall below the maximum limit of 1.0 mg/l specified by [18].

The Iron (Fe^{2+}) concentration varies from 0.020-0.042 mg/l with average value of 0.0295 mg/l compared with 0.3 mg/l standard limit recommended by [18]. Manganese ion (Mn^{+}) concentration values in the water samples range from 0.048-0.035 mg/l, having an average value of 0.0415 mg/l compared to 0.05mg/l that is the recommended limit value. The Mn^{+} at location 9 is relatively high with a value of 0.048mg/l which is very close to the limit of 0.05mg/l of the [18]. This relatively high Mn^{+} content may be related to influence from the environment of deposition which was a marine setting commonly associated manganese deposit. However, the Mn ion concentrations are safe and still fall less than the

maximum limit of 0.05 mg/l specified by [18]. The manganese and calcium elements enrichment in the water samples further buttress the fact that the Kalambaina limestone is a marine limestone unlike the continental limestone referred to it by [8]

Hence, values of the cations in the analyzed water samples of Wamakko Town suggest that the aquifer is a marine limestone deposit which contains relatively high elemental components which readily dissolved into the solution from the overlying beds and limestone aquifer. The marine limestone described here further substantiate earlier workers' description of the Kalambaina Limestone as being fossiliferous marine deposit. The effect of weathering and mineral dissolution in sedimentary basins cannot be compared with Basement Complex which contains minerals such olivine, pyroxene, amphibolites, feldspar, mica and quartz in varying composition depending on the rock type in higher concentration than sedimentary rocks[17].

The anions such as Cl^{-} , F^{-} , NO_3^{-} and SO_4^{2-} ions have concentration values lower than the WHO maximum limits. The Nitrate (NO_3^{-}) ions concentration varies between 0.020-0.053 mg/l with an average value of 0.0393 mg/l, compared to WHO standard limit of 45 mg/l. Sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) ion concentration varies between 0.024-0.150 mg/l with an average value of 0.0697 mg/l compared to WHO standard limit of 250 mg/l. Chlorine (Cl^{-}) ion concentration varies between 3.220-5.430 mg/l with the average value of 3.982 mg/l. The Cl^{-} ion concentration value is within the WHO standard limit of 250 mg/l value.

Fluorine (F^{-}) ion concentration shows no dissolution into the groundwater with 0 mg/l, thus, it is within the WHO standard limit of 1.4 mg/l. However, the NH_4^{+} and PO_4^{2-} recorded concentration values greater than the recommended limits (Table 2). The Ammonium (NH_4) ion concentration varies between 3.2-5.2 mg/l with an average value of 4.21 mg/l, compared to maximum recommended level of 0.5 mg/l. Here, an anomaly with high values was noticed; greater than WHO concentration standard limit. The same phenomenon was observed in the case of Phosphate (PO_4) ion, where the concentration values recorded in the 10 samples show a value range between 0.4-1.2 mg/l with an average value of 0.7 mg/l, greater than the WHO standard limit of 0.3 mg/l.

The high concentrations in the ammonia and phosphate compounds in the analyzed samples are suggested to have resulted from two different means. Firstly, it could be as result of an anthropogenic source, whereby, due to the applications of fertilizer to crops during farming activities in the area. Excessive application of fertilizer in the investigated area over a longtime may have resulted into the decomposition and dissolution of the ammonia and phosphate compounds present in the fertilizer composition.

The dissolved or decomposed fertilizers components (NH_4 and PO_4) would have been leached and percolated through the different layers of sediments before they got in contact with the groundwater, thereby, increased the concentration of such compounds in the groundwater system. These anomalous concentrations recorded in the compounds and the reasons opined here are in tandem with the observations made in the work of [17] on studied areas such as Old Town, Badariya and Bayankara in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Secondly, the elemental compounds could have resulted from the environment of deposition of the aquifer materials in which the phosphate ion might have been contemporaneously deposited along with the aquifer in marine environment [19]. Therefore, this can be the source that is responsible for the high concentration of phosphate.

Ammonium ion (NH_4), though it is a less

essential compound needed by human in water, therefore, [20] stated that ammonia has a toxic effect on human body only if the intake is higher than the capacity to detoxify, at a dose of more than 100 mg/kg of body weight per day. Its high concentration in human system would influence metabolism by shifting the acid-base equilibrium, disturbing the glucose tolerance equilibrium, and reducing the tissue sensitivity to insulin. Phosphate ion (PO_4) is an essential element needed by man. However, [20], stated that too much of phosphate in human consumption can cause health problems, such as kidney damage and osteoporosis.

The Figure 2 summarizes the concentration values for the cations in graphical form. The cation with the highest concentrations are Sodium (Na), Potassium (K), and Calcium (Ca). The moderate to low concentration value ions are Magnesium (Mg), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe) and Manganese (Mn) in decreasing order. However, the relative distribution of ion concentrations in relation to the various locations is well detailed below:

Figure 2: Summary of geochemical analysis of Cation element in the Wamakko Town

Sodium (Na⁺)

The Na⁺ concentration shows the lowest value of 25.4 mg/l, at Locations 2, 4, 6, and 8; while the highest value of 44.2 mg/l is associated with Location 3. These values are less than the

maximum concentration limit specify by WHO put at 200 mg/l in (Fig. 3). The Na ion concentration is likely to remain low and below the maximum concentration required by WHO for the next ten years.

Figure 3: Variation plot of Na⁺ ion concentration in Wamakko town

Potassium ion (K⁺)

Potassium ion (K⁺) concentration have the lowest value of 14.2 Mg/L, highest value of 44.1 mg/l and an average of 31.29 mg/l compared to 200 mg/l of WHO standard in (Tab. 4). Thus, K⁺ concentration is safe and fall less than the maximum limit of 200 mg/l specified by [18]. The distribution of K⁺ concentration in the

locations investigated shows that locations 1, 2, 5, 6, 7 and 9 are relatively high compared to other location. The difference in the concentration values between the lowest and the highest is relatively high. Therefore, the areas with stable high values should be reinvestigated in the near future in order to monitor the increase in values of the Potassium ion (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Variation plot of K ion concentration in Wamakko town

Calcium ion Ca²⁺

Ca²⁺ varies from 12.50 to 18.60 mg/l, average value of 16.18 mg/l less than the 75 mg/l specified limit by WHO (Table 2). The

distribution of Ca²⁺ concentration in the locations investigated shows that locations 2,3,4 and 10 are relatively high compared to other location (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Variation plot of Ca²⁺ ion concentration in Wamakko town

Magnesium ion (Mg²⁺)

Magnesium ion (Mg²⁺) concentration varies between 3.20 – 5.50 mg/l, average value is 3.636 mg/l, compared to 50 mg/l standard limit of WHO (Tab. 2). The distribution of Mg²⁺ concentration in the locations investigated shows that locations 6 and 7 are relatively high compared to other location, while other locations maintain a fairly equal concentration values (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Variation plot of Mg ion concentration in Wamakko town

Zinc ion (Zn²⁺)

Zinc ion (Zn²⁺) concentration follows same trend with others varying in concentration from 0.33 – 0.64 mg/l, average value of 0.484 mg/l compared

with 5.0 mg/l as standard limit in Table 2. The distribution of Zn²⁺ concentration in the locations investigated shows that locations 2, 3, 4, and 8 are relatively high compared to other locations (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Variation plot of Zn ion concentration in Wamakko town

Copper ion (Cu²⁺)

Copper ion (Cu²⁺) concentrations are between 0.02- 0.5 mg/l, average value of 0.195 mg/l compare with 1.0 mg/l as standard limit in (Tab.

2). The distribution of Cu²⁺ concentration in the locations investigated show that Locations 2 and 8 are relatively high compared to other locations with the lowest value at Location 9 (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Variation plot of Cu ion concentrations in Wamakko town

Iron (Fe²⁺)

Fe²⁺ concentration varies from 0.02 – 0.09 mg/l with average value of 0.0421 mg/l compared with 0.3 mg/l standard limit in Table 4.1. The

distribution of Fe²⁺ concentration in the locations investigated shows that location 5 has the highest value while the other locations are relatively moderate to low in concentrations (Fig. 9).

Figure 9: Variation plot of Fe ion concentration in Wamakko town

Manganese ion (Mn⁺)

However, Manganese ion (Mn⁺) concentration value in the water samples ranges from 0.0001-0.0002 mg/l, average value is 0.00015 mg/l compared to 0.05 mg/l recommended limit value by WHO in (Tab. 2). The distribution of Mn⁺ concentration in the locations investigated shows

that locations 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 are relatively high compared to other locations (Fig. 10).

The recorded Cation values (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn⁺, and Zn²⁺) from the 10 samples are having lesser values compared to the recommended value for drinking water (Tab. 2).

Figure 10: Variation plot of Mn ion concentration in Wamakotown

The anion concentration values vary from location to location. Ammonia and chlorine have relatively high concentrations than other anions

as depicted in all locations. This is followed by PO₄ and SO₄ in lower concentrations.

Figure 11: Bar chart of anion concentration values in Wamakko town

Ammonium ion (NH₄)

The NH₄ ion concentration varies between 3.2-5.2mg/l with an average value of 4.21mg/l compared to WHO standard limit of 0.5mg/l. High concentration of ammonia ions was recorded in all the 10 locations studied. WHO

[20] stated that ammonia has a toxic effect on human only if the intake is higher than the capacity to detoxify at a dose of more than 100mg/kg of body weight per day. It influences metabolism by shifting the acid-base equilibrium, disturbing the glucose tolerance equilibrium, and reducing the tissue sensitivity to insulin.

Figure 12: Variation plot of NH₄ ion concentration in Wamakko town

Nitrate (NO₃)

The NO₃⁻ ions concentration varies between 0.020-0.053mg/l with an average value of

0.0393mg/l, compared to WHO standard limit of 45mg/l, (Table 2). The NO₃⁻ ion concentration value is within the WHO value.

Figure 13: Variation plot of NO₃⁻ ion concentration in Wamakko town

Sulphate (SO₂⁻⁴)

The SO₂⁻⁴ ion concentration varies between 0.024-0.150mg/l with an average value of 0.0697mg/l compared to WHO standard limit of 250mg/l. TheSO₂⁻⁴ion concentration value is

within the WHO value (Tab. 2). The Locations 2, 3, and 9 have the highest values, while locations 7 and 8 have the lowest values.

Figure 14: Variation plot of SO₄²⁻ concentration in Wamakko town

Chlorine (Cl⁻)

The Cl⁻ ions concentration varies between 3.220-5.430mg/l with the average value of 3.982mg/l. The Cl⁻ ion concentration value is within the WHO standard limit of 250 mg/l value (Tab.2).

Location 3 has the highest concentration values compared to other location with relatively lower concentration values (Fig. 15).

Figure 15: Variation plot of Cl⁻ ion concentration in Wamakko town

Fluorine (F)

The F ion concentration varies between 0-0 mg/l with an average value of 0mg/l compared to

WHO standard limit of 1.4mg/l. The F ion concentration value is within the WHO value Table 2. The concentration values are the same without any slight difference (Fig. 16).

Figure 16: Variation plot of F ion concentration in Wamakko town

Phosphate (PO₄)

The PO₄ concentration values show a range of 0.4-1.2mg/l with an average value of 0.7mg/l compared to WHO standard limit of 0.3mg/l. High concentrations of phosphate ions were recorded in some locations studied. The locations

with preponderance increase in concentration values are Locations 2, 5, 6, and 9. However, Locations 1, 3, 4, 7, and 10 are within the allowable concentration level (Fig. 17). WHO (1986) stated that too much of its concentration in water can cause health problem, such as kidney damage and osteoporosis.

Figure 17: Variation plot of PO₄ ion concentration in Wamakko town

4.0 Conclusion

The Geochemical concentrations values of the analysed water samples are all within the limits of WHO recommended for drinking water. However, there are exceptions of NH₄ and PO₄ ion concentration values which are higher in the 10 locations. They have values of 6.0mg/l and 1.2mg/l greater than 0.5mg/l and 0.3mg/l of WHO recommendation respectively. The contaminants might have resulted from anthropogenic means such as excessive application of leached fertilizer and manure. The pollutants are suggested to have migrated through

sedimentary structures which serve as pathway for rapid transmission to groundwater system in the study areas.

5.0 References

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